

Implementation of Weaving Techniques in Products Fashion Men's Ready To Wear

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ABSTRACT

Woven crafts are a form of creativity in creating various kinds of products. Weaving techniques not only use materials from nature such as rattan, bamboo, pandan leaves, but can also use non-natural materials, one of which is textile fabric that can be applied to ready-made men's fashion products. Given the high market demand for men's fashion products that require a new touch to be more dynamic and keep up with the times but still include a little local content by applying weaving techniques to certain parts. The *Anyaman* technique is also a basic technique used in making a piece of cloth, but the process of making the cloth is assisted by a tool called a non-machine loom or ATBM and *Gedog* manually. Therefore, the focus of this research is to find out the opportunities for the application of weaving techniques in ready-to-wear menswear products. This research was conducted using qualitative methods and analyzed through literature study and indirect observation. This research produced a design concept and explored weaving techniques using fabric materials applied to ready-to-wear menswear products that have cultural, functional, aesthetic and marketable values.

Keywords: *Weaving, Fashion Product, Men's Ready To Wear*

INTRODUCTION

In this era, fashion is no longer a necessity but a lifestyle so that it can encourage the growth of the fashion industry even more rapidly. In fashion, we can find product categories that are offered based on the occasion and time of use such as Muslim clothing, resort wear, sportswear, office clothing and so on. Each of these clothing categories is further divided into several classifications such as clothing that is specialized for gender, age, region, occupation, income, lifestyle and so on. Therefore, fashion plays an important role in everyday life, through fashion or clothing, a person's character and social status can be reflected from the clothes worn. Fashion can also be said to be a medium of communication for someone to present themselves to the public. So it is obvious that fashion and clothing are forms of nonverbal communication because they do not employ spoken or written language (Barnard, 2006).

There are many Indonesian designers who produce ready-to-wear or pret-a-porter clothing, both children's, adult men's and women's clothing with their respective designer identities. This also affects the selection of materials to be used such as the use of materials such as cotton, linen, satin, denim. So that

later it will be applied with various techniques, colors and models. Therefore, many Indonesian designers combine materials with various handmade techniques such as weaving, knitting and sequins as applications that can be applied to clothing. These applications can be placed on certain parts according to the design of the garment to make it look more attractive and have aesthetic value. Techniques that are done by hand or handmade also provide added value to the product and automatically increase the price of the product, because the process takes a long time, is full of high accuracy and the results will not be the same as others, especially in weaving techniques whose work requires high accuracy in order to get good and quality results. Usually the materials used for weaving are rattan, bamboo, pandan leaves and others, but for application to clothing can use materials from textiles or fabrics. Weaving is one form of traditional handicraft that has long developed in Indonesia. The development of weaving crafts initially had a simple form as a work of art. Weaving is one form of culture that is included in artifacts. Artifacts are a form of physical culture in the form of the results of activities, actions and works of all humans in society in the form of objects or things that can be touched, seen and documented. Based on the above background, the author is inspired to implement weaving techniques in ready to wear men's fashion products that have cultural, functional, aesthetic and marketable values.

METHOD

This research uses qualitative methods. According to Sugiyono (2010) qualitative methods are often called naturalistic methods because the research is conducted in natural conditions. It is said to be natural because initially this method was more widely used for research in the field of culture and the results of the research are more concerned with the interpretation of the data found in the field. Therefore, qualitative data collection methods consist of:

1. Literature study on weaving techniques and men's ready to wear fashion products. This study was conducted through books, scientific journals, internet media, print media and others.
2. Indirect field observations were conducted through the internet by observing Instagram and Pinterest which aims to observe the potential of weaving techniques that can be applied to ready to wear fashion products and what kind of men's fashion trends are currently taking place.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of indirect observations through social media and websites, it can be seen that the development of ready to wear fashion products is very rapid, especially for adult men and women so that there are very many types or models with various applications or techniques applied as decorative elements of clothing such as embroidery, embroidery, printing and others, giving a new look and style. The appearance of ready to wear clothing products can be said to look more formal or casual with types of styles: casual sporty, edgy style, street style, classic elegant, ethnic and so on. There are 6 basic styles in fashion design, namely sporty casual with the keywords comfortable and simple, feminine romantic which has the keywords soft and girly, classic elegant with the keywords elegant and classy, sexy alluring which has the keywords seductive, exotic dramatic with the keywords unique, ethnic and original and the last is arty off-beat which has an artistic, unique and interesting character.

Therefore, the author was inspired to implement weaving techniques in men's ready to wear fashion products. So that in the process of making the work, there are stages of design that must be done, namely:

Figure 1. Mood Board Inspiration

Concept Design

This concept was inspired by the calm atmosphere of the sound of flowing water and the sound of the wind blowing and the author imagined a calm and clean atmosphere. The inspiration was obtained by using the five senses as the basis and can be processed into a concept development and become a fashion collection. So from the inspiration, the author also thought to be able to apply traditional elements, aesthetic values and must have selling points in creating the collection.

The cultural elements contained in the concept of this creative work are the woven technique and *Opnesel technique* that the author uses in making the work. The chicken technique itself is one of the oldest traditional art products in Indonesia, even in the world. Based on its function, usually Indonesian people, especially West Java, make woven products to support their needs such as tools that can facilitate them in carrying out daily activities such as the need to cook or store food such as *Boboko*, *Besek*, and *Nyiru* without thinking about aesthetic value but prioritizing functional value.

This aesthetic value can be seen from the color, exploration and style applied in a design or work of art. Aesthetics is a science that studies everything related to beauty, studying all aspects of what is called beauty (Sachari, 2002). For this reason, in producing innovative fashion products that uphold the values of craftsmanship in the manufacturing process as an effort to respond to the latest fashion trends that see fashion products not only from aesthetics and function but the manufacturing process, hand skills, and accompanying stories as indicators to determine the economic value of the product (Ramadhan et al., 2022). The design of this collection wants to showcase the beauty, especially from the techniques and patterns of weaving that are characterized so that it will be designed in such a way as to form a unity of modern men's ready-to-wear collection products and have selling value. However, there are aspects that must be considered in designing a collection such as aspects of comfort, basically a product, especially clothing, must feel comfortable when used and that can be done when selecting materials, patterns and sewing techniques used, so that this product can be used in various activities or activities both indoor and outdoor with tropical weather, therefore as a creative actor must further analyze the selection of materials, colors, models or design forms.

The design and model applied must also have ergonomic value because this clothing is intended for men, so the design or model of clothing should not be excessive in terms of design but must be neat, clean

not too many ornaments, comfortable to use and modern, in accordance with the activities or activities of active wearers. Another thing that is no less important is the sales media so that consumers can easily get the product and an affordable selling price so that it will attract the attention of consumers with consideration of the selection of quality materials, the existence of craftsmanship and weaving techniques applied, the existence of local content used and the concept of a ready-to-wear model or design with a modern style.

From the storytelling above, the author makes a moodboard or a collection of images that are compiled as a reference to determine the idea of fashion design to be made. This is realized in the form of a collection of images that function as a stimulus to provide an overview of the overall concept of the work and become an inspiration in product design (Angin, 2021).

Figure 2. Mood Board Inspiration
(Source: Author's personal collection)

The moodboard is called *Pure bliss* which means pure happiness from a sincere heart, everything that is done from the heart and done with good and happy feelings will produce good work. Just like the process of decorating fabrics with handmade techniques (embroidery, beads and so on) requires a good mood, high patience so that the results of the process get optimal results that have aesthetic and natural value. This concept consists of shirts, pants and routers that have clean cuts, with tailoring and modern sewing techniques using the main materials of cotton, drill and linen, so that this casual sporty concept can give an elegant effect in terms of materials, sewing techniques, and handmade techniques used.

The main visual that appears on the mood board is pure bliss. It is a color that gives a clean impression such as gray, light blue, and white as well as a combination of bold color elements such as maroon, dark blue, and dark brown. These colors give a natural, dynamic and modern impression so that they can be applied to several items of men's ready-to-wear clothing products. The silhouettes applied in this collection were I and A silhouette lines by applying oversize patterns on several products such as outer and jacket. This was done to give a solid and modern look. The details in this collection are the white list on some of the shoulders and the outline located at the waist to give a masculine and bold

impression. The composition of each element contained in the mood board is arranged in such a way as to imply the principles of design, where balance and unity become points of interest in every process of making art and design, for example in the placement of weaving exploration and open source exploration.

Figure 3. Design Collection for Men's Wear
(Source: Author's personal collection)

This collection is a concept development from the *Pure bliss* mood board, in one collection consists of 6 look designs where each design has unity and balance to the concept created. For this reason, each element contained in the mood board concept must be applied to each design with a good composition. This collection consists of 3 (three) items, namely shirts, pants, and outers. But for the outer, there are three outer models, namely outer with semi-cut blazer, jacket, and hoodie models. The variation in this collection is a form of consumer freedom to be able to choose items according to their wishes and style in clothing.

Exploration

Linen and twill processing in this study, 2 types of exploration techniques were used, the first is the plaiting technique, the single plaiting technique is a technique where bamboo is woven one by one (single) by weaving step by step and inserting bamboo transversely. The second is the *Opnaisel technique* (pressed folds of straight fabric with varying widths from 0.5cm onwards). Exploration in these two techniques is quite time-consuming compared to sewing patterned pieces of fabric, as it requires skill, measured accuracy in making these explorations.

Table 1. Webbing and Opnaisel Technique Exploration
 (Source: Author's personal collection)

No.	Figure	Explanation
1.		<p>This exploration of weaving techniques uses a linen cloth that has been sewn into 2 parts which have a stitch line on the back of the cloth with a size of 2 cm x 1 meter, then arranged using a single woven technique to resemble a bamboo woven booth. The result is that woven using linen material looks less tidy because the surface of the linen cloth is easily wrinkled, making it difficult to arrange.</p>
2.		<p>This exploration of weaving techniques uses twill fabric with the same fabric size as in exploration 1. The technique used is also the same, namely the single weaving technique, but the results obtained are very different, weaving with cloth will produce much neater and more manageable results. Because when pressing the twill fabric, it will be rigid in place and give a neat and clean impression.</p>
3.		<p>In the next exploration, do the same thing, except that this time the exploration uses a type of linen fabric that looks like this fabric has a slightly limp nature and is a little difficult to manage. So that the end result has a little uneven waves, but so that the shape of this weaving remains in place, a list of white taffeta fabric is given as an accent in the exploration so that it is not monotonous.</p>
4.		<p>In this exploration, the material used combines cotton, jeans and linen but the fabric used is the good part (no seam in the middle). The results of this exploration look neater and produce motifs from the color of the fabric used.</p>

From the exploration of these two techniques, the author will use several explorations to be applied to this fashion design. So that later the results obtained are in accordance with the concept that has been designed.

Final Product

Figure 4. Design 1
(Source: Author's personal collection)

Figure 5. Photo Of Work 1
(Source: Author's personal collection)

Figure 6. Design 2
(Source: Author's personal collection)

Figure 7. Photo o Work 2
(Source: Author's personal collection)

Based on the products produced from this research with the title pure bliss, it can be seen that the application of weaving techniques for men's ready-to-wear fashion products that adopt a sporty casual style can be applied. In the design and photo of work 1, the weaving technique is applied to the backouter that extends to the waist and for the other front there is a widening of the collar using white material on the outer tongue and there are also two pockets with a gamblok model equipped with button details so that the outer on the front is not too empty and ordinary. Furthermore, for shirt products, using a basic cut collar with a width of 2 cm with long sleeves and a length of 90 cm that resembles a tunic. The material used in this shirt product is baby twill material so that it gives the impression of being light and neat so that the casual sporty style is increasingly visible when the clothes are coupled with the use of white sneakers and gives an onlook 1 look that seems oversized, comfortable, and modern.

For design 2 and photo work, 2 consists of 3 items, namely outer with a kimono using linen jute material which has woven details on the right front flap to give the impression of piling up and adding straps at the end of the sleeve for a sweet accent when worn. The long-sleeved shirt uses rayon material with a mandarin collar with additional closed details on the front pocket that makes the shirt more dynamic and casual, and pants that have a high waist pattern cut that has a tongue on the front of the pants giving a unique impression but still casual. The pants material used is a type of spring twill that gives a relaxed impression and can be worn on any occasion. In this product, the application of the weaving technique exploration is only found on the outer front flap which is the point of interest in this look 2 which is combined with white shoes with sneakers models so that the overall sporty impression can be seen. Casual style is a refinement of sporty style that makes it more neat and trendy but still comfortable.

CONCLUSION

From this research, it can be concluded that the potential of weaving techniques can be applied and utilized in men's ready to wear fashion products that apply a casual sporty style. The impression displayed has cultural, aesthetic and functional values and has potential selling value. The application of weaving techniques in men's ready to wear fashion products can be designed in such a way as to give a new style or look to the clothes, so that the clothes can still be used for daily activities with the concept of ready to wear. The market for men's ready to wear fashion products is still too safe and ordinary, considering that men lack confidence when using products that are too flashy and trendy, but on the other hand men are still required to maintain their appearance according to their character, needs, and follow ongoing trends (Gunawan et al., 2022). This fashion design consists of a mood board where there are elements of culture, aesthetics and selling points in it, so that it can provide balance and unity as a point of interest in the concept and work.

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